

How the Art Gallery of New South Wales Represents software and hardware environments within its digital preservation system

Mapping PREMIS environmental entities to the AGNSW and Preservica data models

Emulation environments can also be added as a representation to the artwork

More complex example
- Algorhythmic video work

<https://www.artgallery.nsw.gov.au/collection/works/136.2018/>

This is a dedicated environmental intellectual entity/information object under the Structural object

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This IE is linked to artworks requiring this environment for access.